

Methodology details of Towards an Ethogram of Exploratory Process Mining Behavior

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I. INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the details of the methodology used in the paper "Towards an Ethogram of Exploratory Process Mining Behavior." Certain aspects or steps of the methodology will be highlighted and explained at a deeper level of detail.

II. DETAILS OF METHODOLOGY

The following sections describe certain aspects of the main methodology in more detail.

A. BPI Challenge reports

36 BPI Challenge reports by professionals and academics were used as one of the four sources of case studies. An overview of the number of identified reports per challenge can be found in Table I.

TABLE I
OVERVIEW OF BPI CHALLENGE REPORTS

BPI Challenge	Count	BPI Challenge	Count
BPI 2015	9	BPI 2018	3
BPI 2016	5	BPI 2019	9
BPI 2017	9	BPI 2020	1

B. Exploratory process mining

Tukey's [6] characteristics of exploratory data analysis are used to define exploratory process mining. A match with only one of the five characteristics is required to be categorized as exploratory process mining. However, none of the characteristics may be contradicted; otherwise, it is not defined as exploratory process mining. The five characteristics are defined as follows:

This study was supported by the Special Research Fund (BOF) of Hasselt University under Grant No. BOF23OWB03.

- The focus of the analysis lies in getting a better understanding of the data and understanding what the data describes.
- During the analysis, graphical representations play an important role in better understanding the data and what it describes. Visualisations reveal patterns, trends and outliers that might not be obvious from a numerical perspective.
- The focus lies on generating hypotheses and model-building directly from the data. Data exploration without any preconceived notions allows analysts to discover unexpected patterns and relationships that contribute to model and hypothesis generation.
- Robust measures, subset analysis, and reexpression are used during analysis.
- Flexibility and adaptability are necessary conditions. There should not be any strict rules or procedures that have to be followed to conduct the analysis. Using various techniques and tools is highly encouraged, along with the possibility of adapting your strategy as new information is uncovered.

A process mining practice that can be classified as exploratory process mining is process discovery. The focus of process discovery is on discovering the underlying process of the event data and thereby better understanding the data, which satisfies the first, second, and third characteristics of [6]. It satisfies the first characteristic due to the fact that the focus lies on understanding the data. By focusing on building models and graphical representation, the second and third characteristics are satisfied. The fourth characteristic, the use of robust measures, is satisfied due to the use of performance metrics in process discovery. The fifth and final characteristic is satisfied because a multitude of process discovery algorithms exist, which creates flexibility regarding the methodology

used. Conformance checking, on the other hand, is not seen as exploratory process mining as its focus is not on model building or generating hypotheses but on comparing a log with a model or hypothesis. This essentially translates to testing the hypothesis, which contradicts the third characteristic. Lastly, predictive process mining can not be classified as exploratory process mining as it contradicts the first characteristic. Predictive process mining focuses on predicting outcomes or parts of the process instead of focusing on better understanding the process.

According to [6] and [3], exploratory data analysis is an iterative process involving multiple iterations of analysis as analysts refine their understanding of the data through repeated re-examination. Furthermore, in [3], exploratory data analysis is also defined as an interactive process that is not guided by any predefined questions. However, predefined questions are always present in exploratory process mining, even as simple as "What is going on in the data?"

Besides defining exploratory process mining, another important consideration is how behaviors are separated from one another. Often, behavior is defined as the actions that a person performs. However, behavior is much more than that; behavior is determined by many different attributes, such as who, what, where, when, and why [1]. In this paper, we include the what and why to define behavior. The behaviors in the ethogram are high-level behaviors describing actions with a particular intent, i.e. with a specific reason why the behavior is performed. Similar behaviors are not combined into one behavior when the intent of the behaviors is different. For example, the behaviors "Consult with experts/stakeholders" and "Discuss with experts/stakeholders" are not combined due to different intents. The second behavior is intended to validate the conclusions found with experts/stakeholders through discussion. The first behavior intends to extract information that may not be clearly visible in the data by consulting experts/stakeholders.

C. Open Coding

Steps 3 to 6 of the procedure align closely with the steps of open coding described in [5]. His methodology consists of five major steps, which are listed below. These five major steps are conferred into four steps in our procedure:

- Perform an initial reading of the text (related to step 3)
- In the text, identify specific segments that are related to your objective (related to step 3)
- Code the selected segments (related to step 4)
- Reduce overlap and redundancy among the labels by creating categories (related to step 5)
- Create a model with the most important categories (related to step 6)

1) *Step 3: Identify relevant sections where behavior is described:* In step 3, relevant sections that describe exploratory process mining behavior within each paper are selected. These sections are used in the following steps for coding behavior [5]. The purpose of this step is to separate the relevant from the non-relevant sections in the text. Not all sections in the text describe exploratory process mining behavior; those sections

are deemed irrelevant and are not coded. The input of this step is the subset of 16 papers, and the output is all the identified relevant sections within these 16 papers.

2) *Step 4: Code behavior in relevant sections:* Before the coding can commence, an important aspect has to be considered. The coded text is not interpreted as a whole but divided into smaller segments, such that the codes are assigned to segments of the text and not to the whole text. This segmentation, called the level of abstraction, has to be defined in advance at three different levels. First, the *coding unit* defines how small a portion of the text can be to be coded. The *context unit*, on the other hand, determines the largest portion of text that can be coded into a category. Lastly, the *recording unit* determines which text parts are coded [7]. In this methodology, the coding unit is a word, while the context and recording units are paragraphs. These decisions are made with the mindset of not constricting the coding process. The coding unit is chosen as small as possible, while the context unit is chosen as large as possible to ensure that the intent of the behavior can be included while coding. The recording unit is also chosen rather large to ensure we could code all the described behaviors.

In this fourth step, all relevant sections are coded according to the principles of open coding. This entails coding without a predefined set of codes [4]. The purpose of this step is to find behaviors in the text and code them. The input is all sections in the case studies deemed relevant in the previous step. The output is a set of codes.

An example of the coding process performed in this fourth step of the procedure can be found in Figure 1. In this figure, a segment of [8] is coded. In this paragraph of text, six different codes are identified. Each code is assigned to a sentence or a part of a sentence. Certain keywords are sought to code behavior in sentences that describe the displayed behavior and its intent. For example, two keywords are identified in the first sentence: "suggest" and "not long ago". The first keyword indicates that a hypothesis of some sort was made. They make the hypothesis, or they predict that the move occurred not long ago. The second keyword indicates that a time aspect is involved. Combining the two together form the code "Make hypothesis about time". A similar thought process is used for the second sentence. The keywords in this sentence are: "assumed" and "not longer than six months ago". The first keyword indicates that an assumption is made, while the second keyword indicates that it is time-related. Combining the two forms the code "Make time-related assumption". The third sentence is split into two parts. The first part of the sentence refers to the action of filtering, and the second part refers to actions performed after applying the filter. Therefore, the parts are coded independently. The first part is coded as "Filter time" since a timeframe filter is applied. The second part is coded "Compare process flows" since a comparison is made of process flows. The fourth and final sentence of the paragraph is also divided into two parts. The first part describes the timeframe selection, while the second part describes interpretations of the process flows. The first part

Fig. 1. Example of coding

of the sentence is coded as “Select timeframe” due to the keywords “selecting” and “timeframe”. The last part does not have very specific keywords that can be used to code the behavior. The sentence’s meaning is used to make a code, namely “Interpret process flow”. Furthermore, this example also fits with the chosen level of abstraction. The coding unit selected is a word; none of the marked text is smaller than a word, and none of the marked text exceeds a paragraph, which is the context unit. The recording unit is a paragraph, and the example is a paragraph.

3) Step 5: Reduce overlap and redundancy among codes:

After coding all the 16 selected papers, the codes are revised and combined into categories. The list of codes found in Step 4 will be long and contain overlap and redundancy. To remove both, the list is reviewed, and similar behaviors are combined into one category. The goal is to refine the list from Step 4, which serves as the input of Step 5, and create a shorter, more precise list of categories, which is the output of Step 5.

The example displayed in Figure 1 also demonstrates the execution of step 5, where codes are combined into categories. In the previous step, six codes are identified. These codes need to be reviewed to reduce overlap and redundancy. The codes “Filter time” and “Select timeframe” are combined into the category “Apply a time filter”. Both codes describe the same action: filtering data based on a time aspect. Therefore, they are combined into one category. The other four codes are put into more general categories to reduce the number of codes describing the same behavior action. For instance, the code “Make hypothesis about time” is transformed into “Make hypothesis” to combine all the codes that describe making a hypothesis about a certain aspect. The same logic is followed for the code “Make time-related assumption”. Lastly, the code “Interpret process flow” is changed into the category “Interpret process”, also to make it more general. The codes had to be made more general to reduce the number of categories and to make the final ethogram more comprehensible and easier to use.

D. Step 6: Develop ethogram

The input of this last step is the revised coding list. This list is transformed into a systematic framework dividing behaviors into different phases. However, before dividing the behaviors into phases, the categories from the coding lists are transformed into behaviors. This entails combining categories with the same purpose into one behavior. For example, the

categories such as “Calculate frequency”, “Calculate mean”, and “Calculate wait times” are all combined into the behavior “Calculate metric”. Another example can be found in Figure 1. The category “Apply a time filter” is combined with other kinds of filters to the behavior “Apply a filter” in the ethogram. Each behavior included in the ethogram is accompanied by a clear and concise definition [2]. This step aims to translate the found categories into actual behaviors together with the intent of the behavior. The input of this step is the list of categories formed in the previous step, and the output is an ethogram describing exploratory process mining behavior.

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